

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Data Platform

D1.1 ELIXIR Data Platform Annual report 2024

Tier: Technology

Priority Area: Data Platform ([2024-TECHNOLOGY-Data](#))

Executive Summary

The ELIXIR Data Platform achieved significant progress in 2024 towards enhancing data resource coordination and advancing FAIR principles across European bioinformatics infrastructure. Key achievements included the successful hybrid Annual Face-to-Face Meeting in Padova, advancement of the Multi-omics Adapter for Repository Submissions (MARS) initiative, development of the APICURON credit recognition system, engagement with academic publishers to understand current policies and promote FAIR-centric practices, and completion of the 2024 Periodic Review of Core Data Resources and Deposition Databases. The Platform encountered various challenges, including compatibility issues between repository upload tools and metadata standards for multi-omics data and barriers in implementing a recognition system that respects GDPR requirements. Despite these challenges, substantial progress was made in developing community-driven tools and integrating gamification elements to support community engagement. The Platform is well-positioned for 2025 with increasing collaboration and knowledge exchange between the Data Platform and the other ELIXIR Tools, Training, Interoperability and Compute Platforms, and consulting with key stakeholders as it develops the ELIXIR Community Databases (ECD) process.

Document info

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

WP	Work Package
HDTR	Human Data and Translational Research
CMR	Cellular and Molecular Research
BFSP	Biodiversity, food security and pathogens
MARS	Multi-omics Adapter for Repository Submissions
RDA	Research Data Alliance
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
PID	Persistent Identifier
JATS	Journal Article Tag Suite
BioC	Biomedical annotation format
STAR	Structured Transparent Accessible Reporting
MOMSI	Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID

SIB	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics
HITS	Heidelberger Institut für Theoretische Studien
EMBL-EBI	European Molecular Biology Laboratory - European Bioinformatics Institute
VIB	Vlaams Instituut voor Biotechnologie
ECD	Emerging Community Databases
CDR	ELIXIR Core Data Resources
EDD	ELIXIR Deposition Databases
GBC	Global Biodata Coalition
RDMkit	Research Data Management Kit
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe

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Work Package Level (including Milestones and Deliverables)

WP1 – Management and Coordination (Lead: SIB, HITS, UniPD)

- **Objective:** Ensure coordination, communication, and progress tracking.
- **Key Milestones and Deliverables:**
 - Monthly coordination calls conducted.
 - 2024 Annual F2F Meeting successfully held.
- **Challenges:**
 - Coordination challenges across Nodes, scientific and technical areas
 - Alignment with overall ELIXIR strategy.
- **Next Steps:**
 - Plan for 2025 Platform In-Person Annual Meeting.
 - Continued engagement with other ELIXIR Platforms and Scientific Priority Areas.

WP2 – Connecting and brokering Node contributions to ELIXIR data resources (Lead: EMBL-EBI, VIB)

- **Objective:** To improve the ability of the ELIXIR Nodes to contribute to data resources in an efficient way.
- **Priorities in 2024:**
 - Mapping of existing landscape
 - Identify relevant groups in Research Data Alliance
 - Who should be contacted and how?
 - Multi-omics brokering developments
 - MARS¹ (Multi-omics Adapter for Repository Submissions) Initiative
 - BioHackathon² 2024 followed up from 2023 BioHackathon.
 - Representatives from MGnify, ENA, BioSamples and BioStudies are members of this WP and provide relevant context.
- **Discussion areas:**
 - Standardisation of metadata validation processes (e.g. Aspera, FTP, Globus).

¹ MARS project: <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biohackathon-projects-2024/blob/main/23.md>

² BioHackathon: <https://biohackathon-europe.org/>

- Creation of community-driven schemas and tools for metadata submission.
- Develop frameworks for (meta)data validation across repositories.
- **Milestones and Deliverables:**
 - M2.1 “Definition of the parameters for the landscape analysis” where the parameters for landscape analysis are defined as questions in a survey.
- **Challenges:**
 - Delay in circulating survey due to clarity needed on the data protection requirements of running the survey.
 - Compatibility issues between repository-specific tools and metadata standards.
 - Lack of interoperability between repositories and metadata standards on multi-omics data submissions.
- **Next Steps:**
 - Analysis of survey results.
 - Contacting specific repositories based on the survey results.
 - RDMkit data publication page³ will be updated to include more information on multiomics submissions and how to correctly cross link multiomics data when submitting to ELIXIR Deposition Databases⁴.
- **Longer term next steps:**
 - Comparative analyses of existing intermediary tools.
 - Promote standardised documentation and collaboration frameworks with external initiatives (e.g. MOMSI, FAIRsharing).

WP3 – Recognition and credit attribution of research contributions to data resources (Lead: UniPD)

- **Objective:** Implement systems for the recognition and attribution of research contributions to data resources.
- **Priorities in 2024**
 - Cross-mapping STEERS and EVERSE projects.
 - BioHackathon 2024 Project⁵

³ RDMkit data publication page: https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_publication

⁴ EDD example use case: <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/showcase/linked-cohort-data>

⁵ GitHub activities: <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biohackathon-projects-2024/blob/main/25.md>

- Software credit and recognition, linkages between APICURON & GitHub & OpenEBench.
- Expand Group management capabilities to allow separation of different types of contribution, such as Community vs Professional curators, including separate dashboards, awards and tracking.
- Preparing for integration of Glittr⁶:
 - Contributions are made according to the tasks + the score.
 - Private profiles are invisible within the contributors.
- Publications in a BIP! Scholar profile now include links to the related software/dataset used - retrieved from the OpenAIRE graph.
- OpenAIRE - 20m+ open access publications to determine this eg: footnote detection of repo - they create an entry. Working with software heritage to give these PIDs and also related metadata where possible.
- **Key Milestones and Deliverables:**
 - M3.3 Use cases for APICURON evaluated⁷.
- **Discussion areas:**
 - Progress in the development of the APICURON recognition system.
 - Further explore gamification elements (e.g. badges, leaderboards).
- **Challenges:**
 - Balancing psychological aspects of motivation for community curation with professional curation practices.
 - Technical barriers such as integration with ORCID and other systems (e.g. GitHub actions).
 - GDPR - opt-in solution for “data harvesting” concerns.
- **Next Steps:**
 - Agree level of granularity for micro-contributions and establish what constitutes a submission, number of commits or type etc. and other strategies to fairly recognise include contributions made in other systems such as GitHub.
 - Gamification and award/badge improvements.
- **Longer term next steps:**
 - Implement the agreed contribution quantification system.
 - Refine consent protocols to ensure user privacy in importing and migrating between systems and repositories.

⁶ Glittr website: <http://Glittr.org>

⁷ Zenodo publication: <https://zenodo.org/records/15789620>

WP4 – Scalable curation support from the long tail of biological data (Lead: SIB)

- **Objective:** Increase FAIRness of data resources retrospectively while providing scalable support for biocuration.
- **Priorities in 2024:**
 - Establish partnerships with publishers to promote implementation of FAIR-centric policies.
 - Invited publishers:
 - Pensoft
 - IOP
 - EMBO
 - Pilot scalable curation workflows by the end of 2024.
 - CellTriage
 - Enhance Variomes curation support services for oligogenic variants⁸ (with the Rare Disease community and ELIXIR-BE).
 - Consider following up BioHackathon 2023 “Increasing data evidence by text-fragment references using nanopublications” Ulrike Wittig, Mihail Anton, Alexandre Flament, Matt Jeffryes, Luana Licata, Patrick Ruch, Vincent Emonet, Toshiaki Katayama, Adel Bouhraoua
 - Presented in April 2024 at Biocuration Conference in India
 - Progresses presented at Biocuration Conference 2025 with focus on Biodiversity contents⁹.
- **Key Milestones and Deliverables:**
 - D4.1 A report describing best practices of literature biocuration¹⁰
- **Discussion areas:**
 - Annotation types and formats JATS or BioC.
 - A dual combo of recommendations crossing from lab documentation to curating the data and computational work:
 - STAR Methods¹¹
 - Curating4reproducibility¹²
- **Challenges:**

⁸ Enhance Variomes curation support services for oligogenic variants:

<https://olida.ibsquare.be/>

⁹ Enhancing the SIB Literature Services with annotations to support biocuration:

<https://www.biocuration.org/biocuration-2025-preliminary-schedule-of-talks/>

¹⁰ Zenodo publication: <https://zenodo.org/records/15007096>

¹¹ STAR Methods: Cell Press: <https://www.cell.com/star-authors-guide>

¹² Curating4reproducibility: <https://curating4reproducibility.org/10things/>

- Overcoming barriers in publisher engagement and diversity of “standards” and submission and publication workflow types.
- Automating provenance tracking while maintaining manual oversight.
- **Next Steps:**
 - Prepare for D4.2 on "How to FAIR-ify the long tail of data held in journal article supplementary files or generalist repositories".
- **Longer term next steps:**
 - Encourage shared responsibility between authors, publishers and curators.
 - Align curation practices with publisher workflows and vice versa.

WP5 – Establishing and shaping the landscape of Core and Community Biological Databases (Lead: SIB, UniPD)

- **Objective:** Encourage professionalisation of biological databases, ensuring that they comply with FAIR principles and are fairly recognised and promoted within the ELIXIR community.
- **Key Milestones and Deliverables:**
 - M5.1 Completed 2024 Periodic Review of existing ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Deposition Databases.
 - Summarise key findings from Periodic Review:
 - Sustainability
 - Funding
 - Open Data and Licenses
 - Interoperability and Multi-omics
 - Significant progress on D5.2 A report recommending a list of criteria for Community Databases.
 - Survey of CDR&EDD resource owners to assess feasibility and importance of metrics (e.g., uptime, update frequency).
 - Workshop on the 2024 AHM¹³
- **Discussion areas:**
 - Leverage the interactions with the Global Biodata Coalition to support the CDR and enable broader outreach:
 - Meetings with GBC on Selection and Review.
 - Create a checklist for database assessment and recognition:
 - First draft created during 2024 Data Platform F2F.

¹³ [Defining Database KPIs Beyond CDRs: Enhancing Evaluation of Community Resources](#)

- Preparation for D5.1 Report about the value of curated data resources to support global FAIR-ification efforts including slide mockup of topics.
 - **Challenges:**
 - Standardising sustainability metrics across different database types.
 - Privacy concerns when sharing usage and technical metrics of resources.
 - **Next Steps:**
 - Circulate proposed ELIXIR Community Database process to ELIXIR Communities to gather feedback on database recognition criteria and process itself.
 - Prepare a 2025 AHM Workshop proposal for the ECD process.
 - **Longer term next steps:**
 - Run pilot assessment exercise for ECD.
 - Develop tailored recommendations to support less mature databases.
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Annual Platform F2F Event

Background

The event took place in Padova, Italy, in a hybrid format, combining in-person attendance with remote participation via Zoom. It brought together representatives from across ELIXIR's Work Packages, with a focus on advancing the Platform's goals in the ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2024–28 and fostering collaboration.

Day 1: Morning Sessions

The meeting began with a review of the previous year's event, followed by introductions of participants and alignment of objectives. Discussions began with the Biocuration Focus Group on credit attribution within databases, highlighting ongoing challenges around licensing models and the importance of visible recognition for contributors. Support was expressed for the APICURON¹⁴ initiative, emphasising collaborative efforts to improve attribution practices.

Participants then discussed scalable curation efforts under Work Package 4 (WP4), specifically the application of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles¹⁵ in biocuration and publishing contexts. Issues identified included the need for publishers to uphold higher data standards from submitters, and the delicate

¹⁴ <https://apicuron.org/>

¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

balance between curator workload and submitter responsibility. Community-driven tools and automated pipelines were proposed to effectively address these concerns.

Day 1: Afternoon Sessions

This session provided strategic updates on the Science Tier Priority Areas, Human Data and Translational Research (HDTR)¹⁶, Cellular and Molecular Research (CMR)¹⁷ and Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP)¹⁸ and identified overlaps with the Data Platform as opportunities for future collaboration. Data Platform Work Package 5 (WP5) presented the concept of improving the discoverability and support for data resources through the ELIXIR Community Database label, with a focus on balancing scientific merit with sustainability and quality indicators. WP2 explored technical brokerage between repositories, addressing different submission protocols and advocating for improved metadata validation and schema hosting. There was a particular focus on multi-omics data sharing, driven by collaborations with the Research Data Alliance Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration Working Group.

Day 2: Morning Sessions

The second day started with a focus on the interactions between the ELIXIR Data Platform Work Packages and external initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)¹⁹. The importance of aligning training and engagement strategies across these initiatives was highlighted. Discussions also covered accreditation frameworks beyond traditional publications and explored how training programmes could be further integrated with the development of ELIXIR Nodes.

Further sessions on the second day detailed progress on the APICURON tool within WP3, introducing the concept of adding gamification elements to encourage contributions and discussing whether GDPR compliance is relevant and possible for aggregation and reuse of credit and recognition data about curators. The need for interoperability and integration between different databases was highlighted as a critical area for further development.

¹⁶ [Human data and translational research | ELIXIR](#)

¹⁷ [Cellular and molecular research | ELIXIR](#)

¹⁸ [Biodiversity, food security and pathogens | ELIXIR](#)

¹⁹ [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#)

Actions and Future Directions

Actionable steps for the future were identified, including surveying ELIXIR Community leads on the ECD criteria, and addressing challenges in metadata aggregation and credit attribution. In addition, the increased collaboration between ELIXIR Community Databases and the ELIXIR Tools Platform were identified as key directions for the future.

Year Ahead

Looking ahead, the ELIXIR Data Platform is positioned to build on the progress made across the Work Packages (WPs) while addressing key challenges and refining strategic priorities. The upcoming year will be pivotal in consolidating efforts to improve coordination, increase interoperability, and enhance recognition and support for data resources within the ELIXIR network.

Management and Coordination (WP1) will focus on strengthening the alignment between the Data Platform and the wider ELIXIR strategy. The priorities for 2025 include improving communication and coordination across Nodes and scientific areas, with particular attention to accelerating progress as this Scientific Programme is now fully underway and ensuring timely progress tracking. Plans for the 2025 Annual Meeting will be central to fostering collaboration and addressing ongoing challenges in engagement with other ELIXIR Platforms and the Science Tier Priority Areas. Ensuring effective coordination remains a priority, particularly as the Platform broadens its activities and partnerships.

Connecting and Brokering Node Contributions (WP2) will concentrate on analysing the results of the landscape survey to better understand the current state of multi-omics brokering and metadata validation. The focus will be on improving compatibility and interoperability between repository-specific tools and standards, particularly for multi-omics data submissions. Enhancements to the RDMkit data publication page are expected to provide more detailed guidance on multi-omics data submission, including the cross-linking of datasets. In the longer term, WP2 will work towards standardising documentation and developing collaborative frameworks with initiatives such as MOMSI and FAIRsharing.

Recognition and Credit Attribution (WP3) is set to refine systems for recognising research contributions more effectively. Establishing clear guidelines for measuring micro-contributions and linking them to specific recognition mechanisms, such as badges and leaderboards, will be a priority. Further integration of APICURON with

GitHub and ORCID is expected to improve automation and ensure comprehensive and fair attribution of contributions. Developing a balanced approach to recognising both community and professional contributions remains a challenge, but efforts to enhance gamification and improve user control over privacy are expected to support increased engagement and transparency.

Scalable Curation Support (WP4) will focus on the development of scalable curation workflows and the automation of provenance tracking are key priorities for the coming year. WP4 aims to address the challenge in closing the FAIR gap by converting supplementary data and generalist repositories into FAIR datasets by developing a semantically annotated sample of Europe PMC literature and supplementary data files (e.g., spreadsheets, images, JATS/TaxPub treatments) powered with advanced search functionalities. Preparation for a comprehensive report on enhancing the curation of data held in journal supplementary files and generalist repositories are also underway.

Core and Community Biological Databases (WP5) will continue to refine the process for assessing and recognising ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Community Databases. The findings from the 2024 Periodic Review will inform the development of tailored recommendations to support sustainability and interoperability across database types. A pilot assessment of the ELIXIR Community Databases (ECD) process is planned, with feedback from ELIXIR Communities expected to guide further improvements. Engagement with the Global Biodata Coalition will be key to strengthening global alignment on database evaluation criteria.

Overall, the next phase of the Data Platform's development will centre on improving interoperability and data quality while ensuring that contributors receive appropriate recognition. The integration of user feedback and alignment with external initiatives will help position the Platform to meet evolving research and infrastructure needs.

Dissemination Plans

Zenodo upload and inclusion in ELIXIR Zenodo Community.

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